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¹ **Nature:** **R** -Document, report; **DEM** -Demonstrator, pilot, prototype; **DEC** -Websites, patent fillings, videos, etc.; **OTHER**; **ETHICS** -Ethics requirement; **ORDP** -Open Research Data Pilot; **DATA** -data sets, microdata, etc.

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Table of Contents

Table of Contents	3
Executive Summary	5
1 Introduction.....	7
2 Project Goals	7
3 Project Structure	8
4 Project Summary	9
4.1 WP1 – Stakeholder involvement.....	9
4.2 WP2 – Materials selection and fabrication of specimens	11
4.2.1 Materials and irradiation condition	11
4.2.2 Specimen geometry.....	13
4.3 WP3 – Fracture mechanics testing and post-test analysis.....	14
4.3.1 Validation exercise	14
4.3.2 Round robin on unirradiated materials.....	16
4.3.3 Round Robin on irradiated materials	22
4.3.4 Fractography	25
4.3.5 Small specimen test techniques	30
4.4 WP4 – Modelling in support of WP3.....	31
4.4.1 Models and strategies	31
4.4.2 Assessment of potential size effects	33
4.4.3 Advanced modelling of crack growth.....	37
4.4.4 Supporting simulations for small specimen test techniques	37
4.5 WP5 – Evaluation and guidelines	38
4.5.1 Simple Excel Database.....	38
4.5.2 Large scale yield corrections	39
4.5.3 Test temperature selection	40
4.5.4 Specimen set size	41
4.5.5 Manufacturing recommendations	42
4.5.6 Interactions with other projects.....	44
4.6 WP6 – Dissemination, training and education and data management	46

D.7.3 – Final review report

4.7	WP7 – General management	47
4.7.1	Objectives	47
4.8	WP8 – Ethics requirements	47
5	Conclusion	48
	References.....	50

Executive Summary

To investigate the equivalence between fracture toughness data obtained from MC(T) and larger specimens, more 600 fracture toughness tests were performed on six (four base and two welds) different RPV relevant steels in irradiated and unirradiated state. To this experimental round robin, 14 different laboratories participated. In addition, numerical models were implemented in finite element models to support the experimental tests.

For all base materials agreement between data obtained from MC(T) and large specimens is satisfactory when accounting for macroscopic inhomogeneities in the steel (A508 Cl.3 and A533B JRQ). For weld materials, the analysis is more subtle: while agreement between MC(T) and large specimen data is satisfactory for ANP-5 when accounting for material heterogeneity, this is not the case for the 73W weldment, both in irradiated and unirradiated state.

For weldments, the scale of inhomogeneity in a weld was such that a 1T-C(T) specimen would sample across several weld beads, whereas a MC(T) specimen would sample less than a single weld bead. This suggests that metals and especially weld metals can exhibit microstructural inhomogeneity on a scale that significantly affects toughness testing. Both weld and base metals are likely to contain multiple constituent regions of substantial size such as recrystallized and as-deposited regions of a weld bead or islands of ferrite, bainite or martensite that reflect the dendrite spacing typical of castings. Each region contains a distribution of weak links which may or may not overlap with those in other regions. This underscores the necessity of testing a larger number of specimens to ensure an accurate assessment of inhomogeneity.

Finally, we note that all MC(T) complete data sets are inhomogeneous, regardless of the homogeneity or inhomogeneity in the reference data set. The small sampling volume combined with the weakest link theory interpretation means that local differences in the material may result in a large variation from one tested MC(T) specimen to another. Thus, rather than MC(T) specimens misinterpreting homogeneous materials as being inhomogeneous, MC(T) specimens are more adept at identifying inhomogeneity than larger specimens.

This last point should be taken as a strength of the use of MC(T), i.e., the capability to sample material properties very locally if desired. When a complete block or plate needs to be characterized, MC(T) specimens need to be collected from various locations within the block or plate in the same manner as with larger specimens.

Overall, fractography supports the use of toughness data from mini-CT specimens, if the tests are valid according to ASTM E1921-21. Ductility at edges of specimens does not dominate nucleation and the asymmetry of crack front does not dominate nucleation either. The fracture mode is likely to be unaffected by specimen size. A concentration of initiation sites in the central half of the specimen is observed due to the missing side grooves. However, since the relation between K_{Jc} and the distance to the initiation site is unaffected by specimen size, the stress and strain conditions at fracture initiation will be the same in the miniature and larger specimens.

As most important guidelines for MC(T) testing we mention:

- A test temperature selection algorithm was developed based on censoring statistics to minimize the number of invalid tests.
- A data set of 30 specimens or more is recommended to perform a reliable assessment of inhomogeneity according to ASTM E1921-21 Appendix X5.
- A set size of at least 16 specimens recommended to achieve $\sigma_{T_0} \leq 7$ °C.
- In absence of a bimodal or multimodal analysis, an additional uncertainty related to material variability of 7 °C is proposed for a base metal.

1 Introduction

The fracture toughness of a material characterizes its resistance against crack propagation and is an important design parameter to guarantee the structural integrity of components. From several fracture toughness experiments within the ductile-to-brittle transition zone, the reference temperature, T_0 , can be derived by applying the Master Curve approach (ASTM 1921). Here, T_0 defines the transition temperature for a median fracture toughness of 100 MPa·√m for a 1-inch fracture toughness specimen. It is important to note that a shift in T_0 denotes a shift in transition temperature. For example, in the framework of irradiation embrittlement of steels, the shift in T_0 provides a measure for the shift in ductile-to-brittle transition temperature (DBTT).

To assess irradiation embrittlement of reactor pressure vessel (RPV) steels, nuclear regulatory bodies base their evaluation primarily on the semi-empirical methodology based on impact tests on Charpy surveillance specimens. In the framework of long-term operation (LTO) of the present nuclear power plants, surveillance data is scarce, and irradiation space in materials test reactors (MTR) is limited and costly. In addition, the miniaturized size of the specimens limits their activity, which facilitates their handling. Therefore, the determination of irradiation embrittlement on miniaturized specimens is desirable.

Application of the Master Curve approach allows to determine T_0 and hence the shift in T_0 from different specimen sizes and geometries at different test temperatures. As such, miniature compact tension, MC(T), specimens can be used to optimize irradiation space in MTR; or MC(T) specimens can be extracted from broken Charpy surveillance specimens. The latter can provide valuable additional data in the plant's safety case.

The present FRACTESUS project aims to determine the effect of specimen size on the fracture toughness properties. Finite element models (FEM) are used to investigate the difference between large-size and MC(T) specimens and quantitatively assess the resulting loss of constraints due to size reduction. The optimal range of usability of MC(T) specimens can therefore be determined and evidenced with experimental results. Large inter-laboratory testing is included in the FRACTESUS project in an attempt to prove the repeatability and reproducibility of the small-scale testing of fracture toughness properties. Various materials relevant for most of the available reactor materials and irradiation conditions are investigated.

2 Project Goals

The main objective of FRACTESUS is to validate the usage of small-scale fracture toughness specimen testing for safety assessment of reactor pressure vessels (RPV). The work undertaken in the project is aimed to convince appropriate authorities to use MC(T) specimens in the Master Curve approach and finally introduce them to surveillance programs. Validation of MC(T) testing will be performed for a wide group of RPV materials representing different properties in initial and irradiated states, typical for various reactor designs and after the exposition to neutron irradiation. Comparison of results between MC(T) and large specimens supported by numerical modelling will be done and detailed guidelines of MC(T) testing will be prepared. Additionally, changes in codes and standard will be proposed, if necessary.

3 Project Structure

To structure the project, the work is broken down into work packages. The WP structure is visualized in **Figure 1**. In the following, a summary of the project is provided, work package by work package. For details, the reader is referred to the deliverable reports (D1 – D31) [1-31] and technical memoranda [32-35].

Figure 1 – Visualization of the Work Package structure of the FRACTESUS project.

4 Project Summary

4.1 WP1 – Stakeholder involvement

The present work package focusses on interaction with stakeholders of standardization committees, nuclear regulators, nuclear operators, and the international research community. The work package is broken down into four tasks:

- T1.1: Scientific Advisory Committee and End User Group
- T1.2: Current Standards
- T1.3: Nuclear Regulatory Viewpoint and Current Extent of Use by Operators/Research Organizations
- T1.4: Overall Output

The work performed in all four tasks is summarized in deliverable **D1.1** [1] and the technical memorandum by M. Lambrecht et al [32]. The deliverable presents the members of the SAC and EUG; provides a comprehensive overview of different standards governing fracture toughness testing (ASTM E1820, ASTM E399, ASTM E1921, and ISO-12135, ISO-15653, ISO-20064, ISO-22889, ISO-26843 and ISO-27306); and gives an overview of the viewpoints of the different stakeholders with respect to miniaturization of specimens for fracture toughness testing.

The nine main questions, concerns and comments expressed by the different stakeholders towards small scale testing and how they are addressed in the project (text in italic) are summarized as follows:

1. Several regulators and/or operators indicated that they wanted to see more data from small-scale specimens and meaningful comparisons between small and large specimen data so that they could make their own assessments concerning the utility of small-scale specimens.

FRACTESUS has selected several materials, for which data are available on standard specimens, and will produce data on different product forms after different radiation exposures (see WP2). This will significantly expand the amount of data available for assessment.

2. Is the Master Curve the correct description of the mean temperature dependence of fracture toughness and scatter about the mean?

Several regulators accept this for RPV materials while others express concerns. It is not part of FRACTESUS to assess the applicability of the Master Curve. Nevertheless, a large program to provide additional data would be helpful.

3. What is the appropriate size scaling factor?

The Master curve scaling factor of $B^{0.25}$ is based on the assumption that fracture is a weakest link process and, hence, dependent on the volume of stressed material ahead of the crack front. The applicability of $B^{0.25}$ to MC(T) depends on whether MC(T)s meet these criteria.

FRACTESUS will utilize fractography (see WP3) to show (i) how the brittle crack front compares with the specimen thickness (ii) in what K_{Ic} range fracture is a weakest link process (fracture extends from a single initiation site).

FRACTESUS could use data analysis to show the effect on the derived T_0 of (i) using $B^{0.25}$ scaling (or not) on any lower shelf samples exhibiting multiple initiation sites (ii) using (brittle crack front width)^{0.25} scaling if the brittle crack front is found to differ from B .

FRACTESUS can then make recommendations concerning the necessity for fractography and data analysis procedures when using $MC(T)$.

4. What are the appropriate validity limits, i.e., what is the upper validity limit such that it is sufficiently restrictive to ensure that only small-scale yielding with limited crack growth occurs?

Data obtained in the FRACTESUS project may be used to create artificial datasets with different upper validity limits, to test the effect of the limit on the derived T_0 (see WP5).

5. How many specimens are required to derive T_0 ?

It is acknowledged that the precision of an estimate of T_0 is sensitive to scatter and more specimens might be needed. Data obtained in the FRACTESUS project may be used to create artificial representative datasets (subsets of the whole dataset), such that the uncertainty in T_0 as a function of the number of specimens may be assessed.

6. Is the fracture mechanism the same in small and standard specimens, or is it modified by the increased proportion of plane stress in the sample?

FRACTESUS can use quantitative fractography to check (i) that the ductile crack extension prior to brittle fracture is similar at similar K_{Ic} levels in small specimens, (ii) what fraction of the surface exhibits flat fracture (presumed to have failed in plane strain), (iii) that the fracture mode in the region of flat fracture is like that in standard specimens (transgranular cleavage with increasing micro void coalescence as the temperature increases). This information can be compared with information from standard samples, where standard specimen data are available.

FRACTESUS can use initiation site fractography to check (i) whether fracture is a weakest link process (involves a single dominant initiator) in the specimens used to derive T_0 , (ii) the nature of the initiating features (to compare with data from standard specimens where available)

7. Is such a small volume representative?

This is more of a problem when considering a weakest link process rather than a homogeneous deformation mechanism.

FRACTESUS is testing both relatively homogeneous base metals and less homogeneous welds. Based on the outcome of the tests and modelling, FRACTESUS could provide advice on the numbers of specimens required, and suitable data analysis procedures (e.g. involving bootstrapping analysis or other statistical procedures).

8. It would be useful to have a standard that provided advice on procedures for small specimen testing, and clarified procedures when material is inhomogeneous.

FRACTESUS intends to produce information that could be incorporated into testing standards.

9. Are there any fracture mechanisms (for example, grain boundary fractures or carbide-induced fractures in a brittle region) that may occur/occur to a greater extent in MC(T) specimens compared to standard size specimens?

The FRACTESUS project includes fractography, so changes in fracture mode can be observed.

Thus, the FRACTESUS project addresses the above-mentioned questions, concerns and comments.

4.2 WP2 – Materials selection and fabrication of specimens

The present work package focusses on the materials selection and irradiation conditions for the round robins, and the manufacturing of MC(T) specimens from irradiated and unirradiated materials. The work package is broken down into three tasks:

- T2.1: Selection of materials for both irradiated and non-irradiated specimens
- T2.2: Validation of pre-test measurements, comparability of specimens fabricated in different locations, fabrication of non-irradiated specimens
- T2.3: Validation of fabrication of irradiated specimens, comparability of specimens fabricated in different facilities, fabrication of irradiated specimens

The details of the work performed for tasks T2.1, T2.2 and T2.3 are summarized in deliverables **D2.1**, **D2.2** and **D2.3**, respectively. The highlights of these three deliverables are summarized in the following.

4.2.1 Materials and irradiation condition

For the experimental round robin, six materials were selected. The materials were selected following the principles: i) to use both base and weld materials, ii) to cover a wide range of mechanical properties, iii) to cover a range of different chemical compositions, iv) to use pre-irradiated materials as no irradiation campaign is foreseen in the project, and v) to have a well characterized material with large availability of material to make sure all participants can obtain sufficient amounts of material. Details on the materials selection and their initial characterization can be found in [36-37]. A summary of the chemical composition and main mechanical properties are summarized in **Table 1** and **Table 2**.

As shown in **Table 2**, RPV steels were chosen with a large variation in ductile-to-brittle transition temperature (DBTT), yield strength, σ_y , and upper shelf energy, USE, in an effort to cover as many conditions as possible. The considered materials include steels from both eastern and western type reactor pressure vessels. Plates (A533B LUS and A533B JRQ), forgings (15Kh2MFAA and A508 Cl.3), and weld metals (ANP-5 and 73W) are included. The chemical composition, particularly the amount of copper, phosphorus, nickel, and manganese, varies from reasonably pure to intentionally enriched low-alloy steels (see **Table 1**).

Table 1 – Chemical composition of the investigated materials.

Material	Content (wt.%)									
	C	Si	P	S	Cr	Mn	Ni	Cu	Mo	V
15Kh2MFAA	0.15	0.30	0.008	0.002	2.86	0.45	0.10	0.05	0.79	0.31
A533B LUS	0.24	0.41	0.028	0.023	0.08	1.52	0.43	0.19	0.49	
A533B JRQ	0.18	0.25	0.019	0.004	0.12	1.38	0.82	0.14	0.49	0.003
A508 Cl.3	0.19	0.22	0.008	0.001	0.15	1.36	0.93	0.03	0.52	
ANP-5	0.08	0.15	0.015	0.013	0.74	1.14	1.11	0.22	0.60	
73W	0.10	0.45	0.005	0.005	0.25	1.56	0.60	0.31	0.58	

Table 2 – Main mechanical properties of the investigated steels.

Material	Type	Provider	Orientation	σ_y at RT (MPa)	T_{411} (°C)	T0 (°C)	USE (J)
15Kh2MFAA	forging	HZDR	L-S	530	-54	-100	189
A533B LUS	plate	SCK	T-L	455	+34	+12	72
A533B JRQ	plate	NRI	T-L	480	-25	-42	194
A508 Cl.3	forging	CIEMAT	S-L	470	-41	-62	230
ANP-5	weld	FRA-G	T-L	604	-12	-15	145
73W	weld	SCK	T-L	495	-39	-59	135
73W-irr	weld - irradiated	SCK	T-L	662	+55	+42	90

The 15Kh2MFAA steel originates from the original RPV of the nuclear power plant (NPP) Greifswald unit 8 that was never commissioned. It was extracted from the forged core shell ring 0.3.1 in the form of large segments of 0.4 m × 1 m. The fracture toughness samples were fabricated from the middle layers of the forged ring.

The A533B low upper shelf (LUS) steel has a deliberately modified chemical composition (increased P and S contents) to produce mechanical properties similar to those resulted from the long neutron irradiation. The material was extensively tested within the Japanese round robins organized by the Japan Society for the Promotion of Science (JSPS) in 1995 [38]. MC(T) specimens were manufactured from broken halves of 0.5TC(T) specimens.

The A533B (JRQ) steel was produced within the IAEA coordinated research project on “Optimizing Reactor Pressure Vessel Surveillance Programmes and their Analysis” (CRP-3) with the aim of obtaining useful data on neutron irradiation embrittlement [39]. The steel was manufactured by Kawasaki Steel Corporation and was designated by the code JRQ, which stands for Japanese Reference Quality. The chemical composition of the steel was selected with increased contents of Cu and P to create higher susceptibility of the material to irradiation embrittlement. MC(T) specimens were sampled from the inner half of the original block 5JRQ56.

The A508 Cl.3 steel was supplied by Forgemaster Steel & Engineering Limited in 1995 to Equipos Nucleares ESNA for the fabrication of the replacement closure head of the RPV of the NPP Jose Cabrera (Zorita). The material was made by basic electric-furnace processes, vacuum stream degassed and killed, and produced

to fine grain practice by controlled aluminum additions. Remnants of already tested specimens were used to machine MC(T) specimens.

The ANP-5 steel is a modified NiCrMo1 weld extracted from a 6-meter-long RPV test weldment that was supposed to be representative of first generation RPV weldments like Obrigheim or Stade. It was manufactured and post-weld heat treated by Klöckner Werke AG in two segments, each 3 meters long. The material has a high copper content of 0.22 %. MC(T) specimens were extracted from broken halves of crack arrest specimens.

The 73W weldment was produced under the 5th irradiation series within the Heavy-Steel Technology Program conducted in the 1980's by Oak Ridge National Laboratory. Remnants of tested larger C(T) specimens were selected to machine MC(T) specimens.

The irradiated 73W weldment was irradiated in the poolside facility of the Oak Ridge Research Reactor at a nominal temperature of 288 °C and an average fluence of 1.57×10^{19} neutrons/cm² (>1 MeV) in the period 1984-1986.

4.2.2 Specimen geometry

Each participant manufactured their own specimens from blocks that were provided to them. During the manufacturing of both cold and warm samples, all participants completed a survey reporting on the possible problems and difficulties they encountered such that recommendations on the manufacturing and precracking process can be formulated (see WP5).

The MC(T) specimens were designed in accordance with the ASTM E1921-21 standard. The basic design of the specimens is provided in **Figure 2** *Error! Reference source not found.*. Although all participants fulfilled the standard, slight differences in dimensions between the different participants exist. The main dimensions of the specimen are summarized in **Table 3**.

Figure 2 – Standard design of the MC(T) specimens used in the FRACTESUS project.

KIT and PSI used specimen designs with slightly larger total width to ensure a proper fit of their extensometer. None of the participants side-grooved their specimens after precracking.

Table 3 – Details on the specimen design by the different participants.

Partner	Spec. dim. $W_{tot} \times 2H \times B$ (mm)	offset X (mm)	COD (FFD or LLD)
SCK CEN	$10 \times 9.6 \times 4$	0	LLD
NRI	$10 \times 9.6 \times 4$	2	FFD
VTT	$10 \times 9.6 \times 4$	0	LLD
FRA-G	$10 \times 9.6 \times 4$	1.8	FFD
HZDR	$10 \times 9.6 \times 4$	2	FFD
KIT	$11.5 \times 9.6 \times 4$	3.5	FFD
BZN	$10 \times 9.6 \times 4$	2	FFD
EK-CER	$10 \times 9.6 \times 4$	0	LLD
NRG	$10 \times 9.6 \times 4$	0	LLD
CIEMAT	$10 \times 9.6 \times 4$	0	LLD
UC	$10 \times 9.6 \times 4$	2	FFD
PSI	$11.25 \times 10.8 \times 4.5$	0	LLD
CRIEPI	$10 \times 9.6 \times 4$	2	FFD
CEA	$10 \times 9.6 \times 4$	2	FFD

4.3 WP3 – Fracture mechanics testing and post-test analysis

The present work package focusses on the actual fracture toughness tests, their Master Curve analysis and fracture surface analysis on both irradiated and unirradiated materials (see WP2). In addition, as an in-kind contribution, alternative miniaturized test techniques like indentation, small punch and cantilever bending testing were applied to mechanically characterize different materials. The work was broken down in the following tasks:

- T3.1: Fracture mechanics testing of mini-CT specimens on unirradiated RPV steels
- T3.2: Fracture mechanics testing of mini-CT specimens on neutron-irradiated RPV steels
- T3.3: Fractography on tested samples (unirradiated and irradiated)
- T3.4: Supporting experiments based on small specimen test techniques (In-kind)

Part of the results of T3.1 are summarized in deliverable **D3.1** [5]. The completed results of T3.1, T3.2 and T3.3 are summarized in deliverable **D3.3** [7]. The results concerning T3.4 are summarized in deliverable **D3.2** [6]. The highlights of the performed work are summarized in the following.

4.3.1 Validation exercise

Prior to the round robin on irradiated and unirradiated materials (see WP2), an interlaboratory validation exercise of the data evaluation procedures was performed by most of the participating labs. The intention of the validation exercise was to identify and exclude (or quantify) differences in T_0 coming solely from the evaluation procedures of the individual laboratories. No fracture toughness tests were required for this exercise as the test data were provided to the participants. The validation exercise consisted of two activities:

- A1: Calculation of K_{Jc} for a 0.16-C(T) specimen from a given force-COD data set.
- A2: Calculation of T_0 from a given $K_{Jc}(T)$ data set.

4.3.1.1 Activity A1

For activity A1, a typical load-displacement curve was provided to the participants, as shown **Figure 3**. In the frame of this validation exercise, it was stated that the crack opening displacement (COD) was measured at the front face with an off-set of $X=2$ mm.

Figure 3 – (left) Measured force-front face displacement (FFD) versus force curve and relevant parameters; and (right) Comparison of the stress-intensity factors reported by the participants.

From this data set, the participants calculated the J-integral at fracture, J_c , and its elastic and plastic components J_{el} and J_{pl} , respectively, the fracture toughness K_{Jc} and its 1T size adjusted value K_{Jc-1T} . The results for toughness K_{Jc} and its 1T size adjusted value K_{Jc-1T} are summarized in **Figure 3**. Except for CIEMAT, who made no FFD to LLD conversion, the differences are insignificant.

Analysis of the individual results indicate that the deviations originate mainly from the conversion of FFD to LLD. Different participants used different conversion factors: FRA-G used an LLD/FFD ratio of 0.68; PSI, SCK CEN, UC, KIT, BZN and NRG used an LLD/FFD ratio of 0.73; HZDR and NRI used an LLD/FFD ratio of 0.75 and CIEMAT made no conversion (LLD/FFD ratio of 1.00).

In the ASTM E1921-21 standard, an LLD/FFD ratio of 0.73 is proposed provided $a/W \approx 0.5$ and $X/W = 0.25$. However, this is not always true for MC(T) specimens. Some partners utilize specimens where $X/W \neq 0.25$ for practical consideration (e.g. application of extensometers), leading to different conversion factors.

The commonly accepted method of conversing FFD to an equivalent LLD is based on a virtual rotation described by Landes [40]:

$$\frac{LLD}{FFD} = \frac{a+r \cdot (W-a)}{a+r \cdot (W-a)+X} = \frac{a/W+r \cdot (1-a/W)}{a/W+r \cdot (1-a/W)+X/W}$$

with r being the so-called rotation factor. Typical values of LLD/FFD as function of r and a/W are listed in **Table 4**. In conclusion, FRACTESUS partners propose that the FFD to LLD conversion for MC(T) tests should be based on Landes' equation with $r = 0.352$ considering the actual a/W and X/W ratios of the specimen. This procedure is supported with results of finite element simulations in WP4.

Table 4 – LLD/FFD as function of a/W and r .

a/W	0.45	0.5	0.55
$r = 0.352$	0.72	0.73	0.739
$r = 0.5$	0.744	0.75	0.756

4.3.1.2 Activity A2

For activity A2, a typical data set of K_{Jc} values for MC(T) specimens was provided to the participants to validate their procedures to compute the reference temperature via the Master Curve approach. The 1T size adjusted K_{Jc-1T} data set is visualized in **Figure 4**, where the Master Curve approach was applied using the TOTEM software [41]. All participants analyzed the data following their standard procedures that should be consistent with the ASTM E1921-21 standard.

Figure 4 – Master Curve evaluation of the provided 1T size adjusted $KJc-1TC(T)$ data performed by SCK CEN.

All participants reported $T_0 = -100 \pm 0.1$ °C using their own or TOTEM software [41]. Key in obtaining equivalent results was application of the $|T - T_0| > 50$ °C exclusion criterion. Based on this criterion, three test results had to be excluded. Without application of this criterion, $T_0 = -98$ °C was obtained.

4.3.2 Round robin on unirradiated materials

The round robin (RR) on unirradiated materials is based on over 480 fracture toughness (FT) tests performed by 13 different laboratories. For each material, a laboratory performed at least 16 FT tests. A detailed comparison of the reference temperatures T_0 obtained from MC(T) specimens by the different

participants to the ones obtained from larger (mostly 1T-C(T)) is provided in deliverables **D3.1**, **D3.3** and **D5.4**.

In the following, the results of each participant are compared to the results from larger test pieces. For consistency, the Master Curve analysis for the reference data (larger specimens) was redone using ASTM E1921-21 (see ref [37]). In case of inhomogeneous data sets, T_0 is obtained via the simplified method described in appendix X5 of ASTM E1921-21.

4.3.2.1 15Kh2MFAA

For 15Kh2MFAA, the reference values of T_0 were obtained from 1T-C(T), 0.5T-C(T) and 0.4T SENB specimens extracted from the middle layers of the vessel wall. As shown in **Figure 5**, there is little variation in the reference data. Except for the data point from UJV, all data points fall within two standard deviations of the reference value. Thus, the data obtained from MC(T) specimens by the different participants are consistent with T_0 from the larger specimens.

Five out of six results for MC(T) specimens indicate material inhomogeneity, which is inconsistent with the results of the larger specimens. This is likely due to the smaller volume sampled by the MC(T) specimens.

Figure 5 – Comparison of the reference temperature, T_0 , obtained from MC(T) and larger specimens. Orange bars indicate homogeneous material while green bars indicate inhomogeneous material. The error bars show double standard deviations.

4.3.2.2 A533B LUS

For A533B LUS, the reference values of T_0 were obtained from 1T-C(T) and 0.5T-C(T) specimens tested within a round robin organized by the Japan Society for the Promotion of Science (JSPS) in 1996 [38]. As shown **Figure 6**, in the reference values do not vary a lot. All values obtained from the MC(T) specimens

fall within two standard deviations of the reference value for T_0 . Thus, the results obtained for MC(T) by three of the participants are consistent with T_0 from the larger specimens.

Three out of four results for MC(T) specimens indicate material inhomogeneity, which is inconsistent with the results of the larger specimens. This is likely due to the smaller volume sampled by the MC(T) specimens.

Figure 6 – Comparison of the reference temperature, T_0 , obtained from MC(T) and larger specimens. Orange bars indicate homogeneous material while green bars indicate inhomogeneous material. The error bars show double standard deviations.

4.3.2.3 A533B JRQ

For A533B JRQ, the reference values of T_0 were obtained from 1T-C(T), 0.5TC(T) and precracked Charpy-V notch (PCCv) specimens. As shown in **Figure 7**, there is significant scatter in the reference data (larger than a double standard deviation), which is probably due to the macroscopic inhomogeneity in the steel plate [39]. Considering the scatter in the reference values of T_0 , agreement between MC(T) and large specimens is good. Either the MC(T) values fall within a double standard deviation of the reference value, or the reference value falls within a double standard deviation of the MC(T) specimen.

Four out of seven results for MC(T) specimens indicate material inhomogeneity, which is inconsistent with the results of the larger specimens. This is likely due to the smaller volume sampled by the MC(T) specimens.

Figure 7 – Comparison of the reference temperature, T_0 , obtained from MC(T) and larger specimens. Orange bars indicate homogeneous material while green bars indicate inhomogeneous material. The error bars show double standard deviations.

4.3.2.4 A508 Cl.3

For A508 Cl.3, the reference values of T_0 were obtained from 1T-C(T) and 0.5T-C(T) specimens. As shown in **Figure 8**, there is a significant difference between both data points (larger than a double standard deviation), which is probably due to the macroscopic inhomogeneity in the steel plate [39, 42-43]. Macroscopic material inhomogeneity was confirmed during fracture toughness and tensile tests in different sections of the forging [42-43].

Within the scatter of the reference data, agreement between MC(T) and larger specimens is good. The results for the MC(T) specimens tested by SCK CEN, CIEMAT and UoB agree well with the 1T-C(T) results, while the complete MC(T) dataset as well as the MC(T) specimens tested by KIT and NRG agree well with the 0.5T-C(T) results.

Figure 8 – Comparison of the reference temperature, T_0 , obtained from MC(T) and larger specimens. Orange bars indicate homogeneous material while green bars indicate inhomogeneous material. The error bars show double standard deviations.

4.3.2.5 ANP-5

For the ANP-5 weldment, the reference value T_{0Q} was obtained from 2T, 4T and 6T wedge opening loading (WOL) specimens [38, 44]. It must be noted that only a T_{0Q} value was obtained because three data points fell out of the ± 50 °C boundaries [38, 44]. On the other hand, as shown in **Figure 9**, the Master Curve analysis based PCCv specimens yielded a significantly different T_0 .

All T_0 obtained from MC(T) specimens except the one from UKAEA fall within a double standard deviation from T_{0Q} from the larger ones. In addition, accounting for the large scatter in the reference data, agreement between MC(T) data and data from larger specimens is good. The large scatter is likely attributed to inhomogeneities present in the weldment.

Three out of six results for MC(T) specimens indicate material inhomogeneity, which is inconsistent with the results of the larger specimens. This is likely due to the smaller volume sampled by the MC(T) specimens.

Figure 9 – Comparison of the reference temperature, T_0 , obtained from MC(T) and larger specimens. Orange bars indicate homogeneous material while green bars indicate inhomogeneous material. The error bars show double standard deviations.

4.3.2.6 73W

For the weldment 73W, the reference value of T_0 was obtained from 1TC(T) specimens, a combination of 1T, 2T and 4T-C(T) specimens, and PCCv specimens [37, 45-46]. As shown in **Figure 10**, the data from the large C(T) specimens are consistent, but the difference with the PCCv data is significant. All three values for T_0 obtained from MC(T) specimens largely underestimate the reference value of T_0 .

In the FRACTESUS Technical Memorandum by S. Ortner [35], it was highlighted that the scale of inhomogeneity in a weld was such that a 1T-C(T) specimen would sample across several weld beads, whereas a MC(T) specimen would sample less than a single weld bead. This suggests that metals and especially weld metals can exhibit microstructural inhomogeneity on a scale that significantly affects toughness testing. Both weld and base metals are likely to contain multiple constituent regions of substantial size such as recrystallized and as-deposited regions of a weld bead or islands of ferrite, bainite or martensite that reflect the dendrite spacing typical of castings. Each region contains a distribution of weak links which may or may not overlap with those in other regions. This underscores the necessity of testing a larger number of specimens to ensure an accurate assessment of inhomogeneity.

Figure 11 – Comparison of the reference temperature, T_0 , obtained from MC(T) and larger specimens. Orange bars indicate homogeneous material while green bars indicate inhomogeneous material. The error bars show double standard deviations.

4.3.3.2 15Kh2MFA

EK-CER tested 15Kh2MFA (WWER-440) steel specimens in 2007 [49]. The remnants of these specimens were used to manufacture and test MC(T) specimens within the FRACTESUS project. It was hoped that the 2007 fracture toughness tests (measured on $10 \times 5 \times 55$ mm three-point bend specimens) can be compared with the recent results. Unfortunately, it turned out, that the old results are mainly invalid according to the ASTM E1921-21 standard and fair comparison is not available.

4.3.3.3 ANP-4

The MC(T) test data for irradiated ANP-4 material is presented in **Figure 12**. The T_0 cited for large specimen measurements on irradiated ANP-4 in deliverable **D2.1** is -78°C [2], which is within $2\sigma_{T_0}$ of the value derived from MCT measurements.

Figure 12 – MC(T) based Master Curve analysis of FRA-G for irradiated ANP-4 ($T_0 = -66.6^\circ\text{C}$, $\sigma_{T0} = 6.7\text{ K}$, $\sum n_i r_i = 1.61$, $T_{0,scrn} = -66.6^\circ\text{C}$, Homogeneous).

4.3.3.4 Round Robin on irradiated and unirradiated materials: Conclusion

For all base materials agreement between data obtained from MC(T) and large specimens is satisfactory when accounting for macroscopic inhomogeneities in the steel (A508 Cl.3 and A533B JRQ). For weld materials, the analysis is more subtle: while agreement between MC(T) and large specimen data is satisfactory for ANP-5 when accounting for material heterogeneity, this is not the case for the 73W weldment, both in irradiated and unirradiated state.

For weldments, the scale of inhomogeneity in a weld was such that a 1T-C(T) specimen would sample across several weld beads, whereas a MC(T) specimen would sample less than a single weld bead. This suggests that metals and especially weld metals can exhibit microstructural inhomogeneity on a scale that significantly affects toughness testing. Both weld and base metals are likely to contain multiple constituent regions of substantial size such as recrystallized and as-deposited regions of a weld bead or islands of ferrite, bainite or martensite that reflect the dendrite spacing typical of castings. Each region contains a distribution of weak links which may or may not overlap with those in other regions. This underscores the necessity of testing a larger number of specimens to ensure an accurate assessment of inhomogeneity.

Finally, we note that all MC(T) complete data sets are inhomogeneous, regardless of the homogeneity or inhomogeneity in the reference data set. The small sampling volume combined with the weakest link theory interpretation means that local differences in the material may result in a large variation from one tested MC(T) specimen to another. Thus, rather than MC(T) specimens misinterpreting homogeneous materials as being inhomogeneous, MC(T) specimens are more adept at identifying inhomogeneity than larger specimens.

This last point should be taken as a strength of the use of MC(T), i.e., the capability to sample material properties very locally if desired. When a complete block or plate needs to be characterized, MC(T) specimens need to be collected from various locations within the block or plate in the same manner as with larger specimens.

4.3.4 Fractography

Metallographic investigation of the fracture surface (fractography) is an important part of a mechanical test. Fractography provides information on the shape of crack front (fatigue and growth), crack initiation sites and fracture mode. Part of the demonstration of equivalence between the use of large size specimens and MC(T) specimens is to show that the fracture mode and location of crack initiation points is equivalent.

Several partners have performed fractography on all materials in the round robins. To obtain high quality and compatible results between the different laboratories, all partners followed the same guidelines and procedures outlined in the technical memorandum S. Ortner et al [33]. The detailed results are described in deliverables **D3.1** and **D3.3**. Some highlights (representative to all investigated materials) are summarized in the following.

4.3.4.1 *Fatigue crack front and ductile crack growth*

During precracking of MC(T) specimens, a large fraction of the precracks exhibited a significant asymmetry. Fatigue precracking is very sensitive to small deviations from the intended geometry, such as misorientation of the load-pin-holes or slightly deformed load pins. Such deviation are easier to occur in MC(T) specimens due to the tighter relative tolerances.

Nevertheless, the majority of the precracks shown fulfill the requirements of ASTM E1920-21, sections 8.8.1/8.9.1. Moreover, it was found that asymmetry does not affect the location of the initiation site in MC(T)s, as shown for example in **Figure 13**.

The ductile crack extensions were also measured according to ASTM E1920-21. As general tendency, it was observed that the frequency and length of ductile crack extension increased with higher test temperatures. It could not be verified, whether there is a significant difference as compared to larger specimens in this respect – as suitable Δa data from large specimens of the steels tested in FRACTESUS are not available in the literature. However, it is well understood that the onset of large scale yielding and associated loss of constraint takes place at lower K_{Jc} values in MC(T) specimens as compared to larger ones [8, 50-51].

Figure 13 – Crack fronts and initiation site locations, material ANP-5 mini-CT samples tested by UC.

4.3.4.2 Slant fracture

We define slant fracture as the lateral width of the shear lips. The sides of a test specimen are not in plane strain and fail in a more ductile mode than the main part. The specimen size criteria for valid toughness testing are designed to ensure that the failure process is dominated by plane strain and small-scale yielding. The dominance of plane strain and small-scale yielding can be demonstrated by showing that the proportion of the specimen exhibiting slant fracture is small. The width of the slant fracture is measured in the near crack front half of fracture surface, at five, evenly spaced locations (see Figure 14). These measurements are averaged into a single slant fracture value.

Figure 14: Example of slant fracture measurement (material ANP-5)

The effects of testing temperature and fracture toughness values on slant fracture were investigated. Examples are shown in **Figure 15**. There is no clear effect of the normalized test temperature or K_{Jc} on the slant fracture.

Figure 15: Slant fracture as function of $T - T_0$ (left) and as function K_{Jc} (right).

4.3.4.3 Fracture modes

The characterization of the fracture surface of FT specimens is realized by the assignment of subareas to the following categories:

1. Cleavage
2. Ductile micro-void coalescence
3. Particle
4. Secondary crack
5. Impurity intergranular
6. Unclear

It must be noticed that this categorization is sometimes diffuse and is affected by the operator's experience. In **Figure 16**, the analysis of selected samples from all materials tested at HZDR is shown. Samples tested at temperatures as close as possible to $T_0 - 25^\circ\text{C}$ were selected; the overall temperature range was $-33^\circ\text{C} < T - T_0 < -18^\circ\text{C}$. Most of the tests were found to be associated with cleavage or mixed ductile/cleavage fracture.

Figure 16 – Fracture modes of selected HZDR samples (from all materials), tested at $T - T_0 \approx -25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. Average percentage of all surface features per material.

4.3.4.4 Initiation site locations

The identification of initiation site locations is based on chevron markings and river lines. We are interested in (i) the distance of the initiator from the fatigue precrack in the crack plane, and (ii) the distance of the initiator from the specimen side in thickness direction (lateral position).

As for the lateral positions, it was found that the majority of initiation sites is located in the central half of the specimen (see **Figure 17**), well away from the regions of slant fracture and within the parts of the specimen calculated to be in small-scale yielding by the Nevalainen and Dodds [52] analysis. Moreover, there is no correlation between lateral distance and distance from the crack front (right chart).

Figure 17: Left: Cumulative probability of the normalized lateral distance of initiation sites for materials ANP-5 and A533B-LUS (tests by UC); right: x-distance vs. lateral distance for material SA 508 Cl3 (tests by KIT).

It seems very likely that the strong concentration of the initiators in the specimen center is due to the missing side grooves in all tested MC(T)s. A comparison with of our MC(T) data with literature data from larger specimens [53-54] showed that these data are consistent as long as the fracture is transgranular. Larger uncertainties of the initiations site locations are observed if significant intergranular fracture is involved (**Figure 18**). Since the relation between K_{Jc} and the distance to the initiation site is unaffected by specimen size, the stress and strain conditions at fracture initiation will be the same in the miniature and larger specimens.

Figure 18 – Fracture toughness K_{Jc} plotted against the distance from crack front; Fractesus data in comparison to 0.4T SE(B) data from KAERI.

4.3.4.5 Detailed initiation site characterization

Once the initiation site locations were identified, a characterization of the composition of selected sites was performed – based on EDX spectra and high-magnification images. Thus, the initiation sites can be assigned to one of the following types [55]:

- Carbides
- Metal-rich inclusions
- MnS inclusions
- Oxide particles
- Grain boundary initiation
- Intergranular fracture

In case of intergranular fracture, it is not possible to determine the exact location of brittle fracture initiation. In **Table 5**, the identified types of initiators are listed per material.

Table 5 – Overview on types of initiations sites identified for the FRACTESUS materials.

Material	Initiation types found	Comment
15Kh2MFAA	MnS inclusions, oxide particles containing Si, Al, Cr, V and Ti; intergranular fracture	MnS inclusions sometimes are connected to smaller (Cr,Mn)-rich carbides, which may be the actual initiation particle.
A533B JRQ	Intergranular fracture, Mo-rich carbides; grain boundary initiation	
HSSI-73W	Oxide particles containing Si, Al, Mn and S; Mo-rich carbides	
SA508 Cl.3	Grain boundary initiation; Mo-rich carbides;	
ANP-5	Oxide particles containing Si, Al, Mn and S	Only considering batches CD8M2, CD8M3
A533B LUS		Particles were not observed in SEM images, EDX has not been done.

4.3.4.6 Fractography: Summary

Overall, fractography supports the use of toughness data from mini-CT specimens, if the tests are valid according to ASTM E1921-21. Ductility at edges of specimens does not dominate nucleation. The asymmetry of crack front does not dominate nucleation either. The fracture mode is likely to be unaffected by specimen size. A concentration of initiation sites in the central half of the specimen is observed due to the missing side grooves. However, since the relation between K_{Ic} and the distance to the initiation site is unaffected by specimen size, the stress and strain conditions at fracture initiation will be the same in the miniature and larger specimens. Detailed analysis of the initiation sites was done in a few samples. The brittle fracture initiates at oxide particles in weld materials, at carbides, grain boundaries or within intergranular fractured areas in base metal steels. However, a direct comparison with standard sized samples was not possible due to lack of data.

4.3.5 Small specimen test techniques

As in-kind contribution to the FRACTESUS project, CCFE, HZDR, UC, BZN and UoB have executed additional supporting tests based on small specimen technologies, namely, small punch (SP) tests, indentation tests, and cantilever bending tests. The detailed description of the performed work is provided in deliverable **D3.2**.

The main conclusion from the small punch test campaign is that the derived transition temperature is linearly proportional to the Charpy test derived transition temperature. The proportionality factor α is $\alpha = 0.43$ for T_{41J} and $\alpha = 0.42$ for T_{47} .

The main conclusion of the ball indentation tests on 15KH2MFAA is that this technique can be used with a sufficient degree of accuracy to determine the flow curves.

The cantilever bending tests have shown that the un-irradiated 73W materials are ductile at room temperature, meaning that the specimens sustained significant deflection without fracture. Although it is possible to study the plastic deformation behavior of the material, future plans to measure the fracture toughness using cantilever bending tests would require a test at much lower temperature, where the material would behave brittle and thus enable the fracture during the bending.

4.4 WP4 – Modelling in support of WP3

The present work package concerns purely numerical work in support of the exploitation, understanding and analysis of the experimental results of WP3. The objectives are to i) define and validate a modelling strategy for interpretation of the experimental data; ii) assess the potential size effect between M-C(T) and 1T-C(T) based on this modelling; and iii) support the evaluation and interpretation of experimental work on small specimen test techniques.

The work package consists of two main tasks:

- T4.1: Fracture mechanics simulations using C(T) specimens
- T4.2: Supporting simulations based on small specimen test techniques

The detailed results from T4.1 and T4.2 are reported in deliverables **D4.1** and **D4.2**, respectively. Deliverable **D4.3** provides a summary of all the work performed in the work package.

In the following, the highlights of the work performed in this work package are described. For more details the reader is referred to the relevant deliverables.

4.4.1 Models and strategies

First, a simple and robust method of flow curves determination using tensile test data and inverse FEM was developed and applied to 73W in both the unirradiated and irradiated condition and tested at various temperatures [56]. The method allows to extract flow curves for all investigated materials and testing conditions, giving excellent reproduction of almost the whole range of tensile tests when applied in the numerical model of tensile specimens.

Then FEM of MC(T) and 1T-C(T) specimen geometries were developed. As each laboratory uses its own (commercial) software and model parameters, a validation exercise was performed to ensure that each laboratory obtains equivalent results. The nine participants all simulated the test case: a prescribed load displacement for a given material at two different temperatures for both the MC(T) and 1T-C(T) geometry. The different options chosen by the participants are summarized in **Table 6**.

Comparison of the macroscopic data (load, displacements of the interest points, plastic volume, J -integral calculated by the standard) and the local mechanical fields (maximum principal stress, plastic strain, triaxiality, on the middle and external faces for 3 loading levels) showed equivalent results between the nine participants. For example, the maximum obtained stress, stress triaxiality and equivalent plastic strain obtained by the nine participants is shown in **Figure 1**. The few differences concern mainly the level of plastic strain reached at the crack tip for the highest loading levels; these differences may be due to the interpolation necessary to extrapolate the field values which are defined at the integration points, and which are extrapolated here to the mesh nodes.

A similar validation exercise with four participants was performed to model brittle fracture of C(T) specimens using the Beremin model [57]. Application of each participant's model to the same material under the same conditions resulted in the Weibull stress and failure probability as a function of stress intensity. As shown in **Figure 20**, all participants obtained equivalent results.

Table 6 – Overview of the different models and model settings used by the different participants.

		SCK CEN	NRI	CEA	IRSN	KIT	BZN	KTU	PSI	CRIEPI
Finite element software		ANSYS 2021 R2	ABAQUS 2019	Cast3M20	XPER r2465	ABAQUS 2019	MSC.Marc Mentat 2020 FP1	ANSYS 2020 R2	ABAQUS	MSC.Marc 2019
Pin material	Stiff pin with zero friction	X	X					X	X (1T-CT only)	
	Additional chunk of material			X	X	X	X	X	X (MCT only)	X
J-integral calculation	ASTM	X		X	X	X	X	X	X	X
	FEM		X				X		X	
Crack tip meshing		$N_r = 50,$ $N_\theta = 12,$ $N_z = 10$	$N_r = 50,$ $N_\theta = 12,$ $N_z = 10$	$N_r = 50,$ $N_\theta = 12,$ $N_z = 10$	$N_r = 50,$ $N_\theta = 12,$ $N_z = 10$ (+ refinement on the specimen surface side)	$N_r = 50,$ $N_\theta = 12,$ $N_z = 10$	$N_r = 50,$ $N_\theta = 12,$ $N_z = 10$ (+ refinement on the specimen surface side)	$N_r = 50,$ $N_\theta = 12,$ $N_z = 10$ (MCT)	$N_r = 50,$ $N_\theta = 12,$ $N_z = 20$ (+ refinement on the specimen surface side)	$N_r = 79$ (400 μm), $N_\theta = 20,$ $N_z = 10$
Number of elements	MCT	39 975	19 960	12 960	27 280	25 940	17 970	42 358	85 740	42 290
	1T-CT	63 558	24 120	22 340	26 840	29 230	23 820	53 973	103 446	37 980
Number of nodes	MCT	177 986	86 249	58 753	122 264	116 822	81 399	178 960	257 657	187 959
	1T-CT	278 062	108 452	100 340	120 340	131 193	107 258	224 658	192 574	168 722
Number of integration points per element		8	8	8	27	8	27	8	8 around the crack tip (linear elements far away)	27
Data extraction points	Initial mesh	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X

Figure 19 – Maximum obtained value of (left) the principal stress, (middle) stress triaxiality, and (right) plastic strain obtained by the different participants.

Figure 20 – (left) Weibull stress and (right) failure probability as a function of stress intensity factor obtained by the different participants.

Given that the different models implemented by the participants provide equivalent results, the models as such need to be tested by verifying that they can predict the mechanical behavior of the specimens under relevant conditions. The first results concerning the comparison between 1T-C(T) and MC(T) specimens were analyzed and lead to the following conclusions:

- By normalizing the applied load and displacement, the curves for both 1T-C(T) and MC(T) geometries overlap, indicating a robust correlation between different specimen sizes. In the elastic regime, the stress intensity factor (SIF) evolution with normalized displacement is identical for both geometries but diverges in the plastic regime due to the larger plastic area in the 1T-C(T) specimens.
- The maximum principal stress values are similar for both geometries, although the plastic zone is longer in MC(T) specimens. This results in the maximum stress occurring further from the crack tip in MC(T) specimens compared to 1T-C(T) specimens.
- The maximum equivalent plastic strain value is higher in the MC(T) than in the 1T-C(T) specimens.

The study reveals that the stress triaxiality is lower in MC(T) specimens compared to 1T-C(T) specimens due to the greater contribution of stress in the thickness direction in the larger specimens. This lower triaxiality in MC(T) specimens contributes to a more plane stress conditions, affecting the fracture behavior analysis.

4.4.2 Assessment of potential size effects

As shown in the previous section, the numerical tools constitute a robust base for the evaluation of the potential size effects of MC(T) specimens compared to 1T-C(T) specimens. Five studies were performed to study the influence of i) crack length on the FFD to LLD conversion factors, ii) precrack non-uniformity on brittle fracture initiation, iii) side grooves, iv) specimen geometry on T_0 , and v) loss of constraints.

4.4.2.1 The influence of crack length on conversion factors

For the calculation of the J integral, the CMOD at the load line is required according to the ASTM standard. Because of practical considerations, however, some laboratories measure the displacement at the front face (FF) instead of the load line (LL). As already discussed in WP3, an appropriate conversion between FF

and LL displacement is necessary. In the following, the influence of initial crack length on the conversion factors is studied.

For the cases $X/W = 0.25$ and $X/W = 0.44$, the results indicate that there is no need to introduce factor evolution during loading using the FRACTESUS formula based on the virtual rotation point by Landes [40] (see WP3). This means that for the standard MC(T) geometry the recommended factor of 0.73 in the standard is sufficient for all initial crack lengths, and that the equation proposed by Landes [40] can be used to determine the conversion factor for any X/W ratio.

4.4.2.2 The influence of precrack non-uniformity

A lot of MC(T) specimen test results are censored due to precrack non-uniformity. In this scope, Li et al [58] studied the effect of the precrack non-uniformity on the initiation of brittle fracture. This initiation is controlled by the crack front maximum principal stress and the fracture process zone size. Li et al then evaluated the effect of precrack non-uniformity on those parameters and their consequences on the T_0 values. The reference temperature as a function of the tilt angle of the precrack front is shown in **Figure 21**.

The effect of pre-crack non-uniformity on the fracture toughness of MC(T) geometry becomes significant when the tilt angle exceeds 20° , although beyond the existing validity limit of precrack front curvature given in ASTM E1921-19b. The present study suggests that the restrictions on the precrack front curvature can be relaxed. The analysis on the realistic curved precrack configuration suggests that the methodology of applying the validity limit of $\pm 0.1 \times (b_0 B_N)^{1/2}$ on the seven inner points (with minimum $a_0/W=0.44$ and precrack front curvature parameter $C = 0.1$) is an effective option in this context.

Figure 21 – Reference temperature (T_0) evaluated from the uniform precrack configuration and various tilted precrack configuration.

4.4.2.3 The influence of side grooves

In this section different B_n/B ratios are evaluated to determine the one that provides a homogeneous distribution of J values along the specimen thickness. BZN and KTU investigated the effect of machining side-grooves on the mechanical behavior of the MC(T) specimen. Both participants used the meshes described in the validation exercise, adding side-grooves with a 60° . BZN modeled three different geometries to evaluate the influence of B_n/B ratio on the evolution of J . KTU, on the other hand, used a B_n/B ratio of 0.8. The resulting values of the J integral along the specimen thickness for the limiting cases of B_n/B equal to 1.0 and 0.8 are shown in **Figure 22**.

Figure 22 – Evolution of the J values along the specimen's thickness, compared to the global value, for B_n/B equal to 1.0 and 0.8 at $M = 30$.

As expected, the proportion of the MC(T) specimen in plane strain increases when machining side-grooves. It was found that a B_n/B ratio equal to 0.8 allows to significantly reduce the variation of J values along the specimen thickness. However, no notch radius was meshed in the models used. The effect of this notch radius should be evaluated to confirm the interest of machining side grooves in a hot cell environment.

4.4.2.4 The influence of specimen geometry on T_0

In this section the Beremin model constructed during the validation exercise is used to assess the effect of specimen geometry on the T_0 value. To achieve this, simulations were performed on three materials: 15Kh2MFAA, 73W, and JRQ (all in their unirradiated states). For each material, the same temperatures were simulated for both specimen geometries. The result resulting Master Curves for the three materials are shown in **Figure 23**. The results indicate that T_0 measured using MC(T) specimens is lower than T_0 measured using 1T-C(T) (from -26°C to -49°C). Testing the MC(T) specimens at lower temperature may reduce this difference.

Figure 23 – Comparison of the Master Curve and the T_0 values obtained for the 1T-C(T) and MC(T) geometries for the unirradiated 15Kh2MFAA, the unirradiated 73W and the unirradiated JRQ.

4.4.2.5 The influence of loss of constraints

Two approaches were assessed to investigate and quantify the loss of constraints in MC(T) specimens. The first one is based on a local approach to brittle fracture evaluated by PSI, and the second approach is based on the J-Q theory, which is a global approach, studied by CRIEPI. The constraint loss effect on MC(T) specimens were quantified on A533B JRQ steel.

The local approach ($\sigma^* - V^*$) demonstrates that the constraint loss leads to an extra increase of toughness of about 15% in the MC(T) specimens, which is not accounted for in the size adjustments recommended in the ASTM-E1921 standard. The results from the local approach are compared to the ASTM size correction in **Table 7**.

Applying the constraint loss correction and doing the ASTM-E1921 crack front length adjustments leads to an increase of about 10°C of the reference temperature T_0 determined with the MC(T) data, which makes T_0 more consistent with the data from larger 1T-C(T) specimens.

For the global approach, the $J - Q$ theory was considered. The results show that the constraint level in the middle of the MC(T) specimen is well maintained up to $K_{Jc,limit}$.

Table 7 – Summary of the MC analysis on A533B-JRQ according to the standard Master Curve and with additional constraint loss correction.

Dataset	Standard ASTM-E1921 analysis	Analysis with CL corrections prior the ASTM-1921 analysis
UJV	-61.5	-52.9
HZDR	-66.9	-57.1
BZN	-58.0	-54.3
CRIEPI	-65.1	-55.3
UKAEA	-65.4	-53.3
Combined MCT data	-63.5	-55.2
Larger specimens 1T C(T)	-53.6	

4.4.3 Advanced modelling of crack growth

To fully capture the evolution of the mechanical behavior of RPV steels in the ductile-to-brittle transition zone, it is necessary to numerically reproduce the variability in fracture toughness observed experimentally. The goal of this section is to propose models that can simulate unstable crack propagation at low temperatures and stable propagation at high temperatures. To do so, two cohesive zone models (CZM) were developed.

IRSN and KIT proposed a calibration method of the CZM parameters to model MC(T) fracture toughness tests in the ductile-to-brittle transition. In particular, the method proposed by IRSN allows to account for the scatter in the ductile to brittle transition (DBT). However, the failure probability of a specific simulation must be known a priori.

KIT calibrated the material and cohesive parameters using experiments they performed. A triaxiality dependent cohesive model was considered. They compared the result with standard C(T) specimens but using the CZM parameters calibrated on MC(T) tests. The cohesive model is supposed to be unable to model the size effects, and so the results were supposed to be equivalent in terms of fracture toughness. However, the standard C(T) simulations led to slightly higher toughness, so the model in its present form cannot predict the experimental constraint effect. Triaxiality dependent cohesive energy should be introduced in addition to triaxiality dependent cohesive strength.

In addition, KIT started to develop a probabilistic CZM approach to model the scatter in the DBT. First results show a good prediction of the experimentally determined reference temperature, but the numerical fracture toughness scatter is significantly lower than the experimentally observed scatter.

4.4.4 Supporting simulations for small specimen test techniques

This section involves FEM simulations of the small punch test, ball indentation test and notched tensile test. This activity aims at supporting the evaluation and interpretation of experimental results performed in task T3.4. The main conclusions are summarized as:

- Axisymmetric FEM simulation of SP, notched tensile and spherical indentation tests are sufficient (no need for 3d models).
- Variation of element number per thickness of the specimen was used in a range from 2 elements to 16 elements first and second order. Both linear and nonlinear (second order) elements demonstrated that 10 elements per specimen thickness is sufficient to achieve a stable result and for the second order elements even 4 elements are giving the results close to the final stable value.
- In SP simulations, the punch and the specimen holder can be modelled as rigid bodies.
- For the ductile damage model (GTN), multiple optimum parameter sets exist, all providing a good agreement between simulated and experimental force-deflection/displacement curves $F(u)$ or $F(v)$.
- The GTN parameters and the friction coefficient affect the late stage of the SP curve $F(u|v)$, i.e. $(u, v) > 1\text{mm}$, while the early stage is governed by the flow curve of the material.
- Friction coefficient and GTN parameters are interdependent and have to be optimized simultaneously.

- The thickness reduction of SP samples leads to a decrease of maximum force F_m and of deflection/displacement at maximum force $u_m|v_m$. The effect of ductile damage on $F(u)$ is slightly more pronounced for thinner samples.
- For the SP test, a modified elastic-plastic transition force F_y was proposed for the empirical yield strength correlation, which provides a significantly reduced uncertainty as compared to the elastic-plastic transition force F_e defined in the European standard.
- With the new definition of F_y , the yield strength correlation is widely independent of the SP geometry and the flow properties of the material.
- Ball indentation test is not suitable for GTN parameter optimization. However, it is suitable for estimating the yield strength and tensile strength of the material with reasonable accuracy.

4.5 WP5 – Evaluation and guidelines

The present work package focuses on the deep analysis of the experimental and simulation results. To facilitate these analyses, a database containing all test data is composed. The results of these analyses lead to best practices and recommendations with respect to the treatment of MC(T) specimens in the frame of the ASTM E1921 standard. In this work package, also the exchange with other ongoing national and international projects is established.

The work package is broken down in three main tasks:

- Task 5.1: Interpretation of results
- Task 5.2: Guidelines
- Task 5.3: Exchange with ongoing projects

The design and construction of the database as well as the summary of all test results and their interpretation are described in deliverables **D5.1** and **D5.3**.

The analyses of comparing experimental fracture toughness tests to finite element model (FEM) simulations and the comparison of the results between large CT(T) and MC(T) are made in deliverables **D5.2** and **D5.4**. Clearly, these four deliverables largely overlap with the deliverables in WP3 and WP4. The guidelines and recommendations concerning the manufacturing and testing of MC(T) specimens in the frame of ASTM E1952 is provided in deliverables **D5.5** and **D5.7**.

A lot of the technical work and analyses on which the above deliverables are based is described in the Technical Memorandum by S. Ortner [35].

Finally, the summary of all interactions between FRACTESUS and different projects is provided in deliverable **D5.6**.

In the following, the highlights of the work package are summarized.

4.5.1 Simple Excel Database

The simple excel database (SEeD) summarizes all parameters that have been measured, determined or evaluated during the project's MC(T) test campaign. In total, it contains the data of 757 fracture toughness tests.

The purpose of this data summary is to allow for an easier final evaluation of all experimental MC(T) test results generated throughout the project and to identify parameters that could possibly affect the determination of K_{Jc} with small scale specimens (for example the elastic loading rate or the straightness of the crack front).

4.5.2 Large scale yield corrections

ASTM E1921 stipulates that the maximum K_{Jc} capacity ($K_{Jc\text{limit}}$) is limited by the specimen's remaining ligament (b_0). The K_{Jc} data that exceeds this limit must be replaced (censored) by the value of the $K_{Jc\text{limit}}$. Clearly, for smaller specimens the ligament reduces and hence the K_{Jc} limit, which may lead to many censored data.

$$K_{Jc\text{ limit}} = \left[\frac{Eb_0\sigma_y}{30 \cdot (1 - \nu^2)} \right]^{0.5}$$

Potential routes to mitigate the problem of extensive data censoring are through introducing a large-scale yielding (LSY) correction (i.e. the fracture model-based reduction of high apparent K_{Jc} values). Two methods were examined within FRACTESUS at>NNL [34] and SCK CEN [59]. The>NNL approach was based on Nevalainen and Dodds' stress-based model of fracture [52]. The SCK method was based on Ruggieri and Dodds' [60] implementation of Wallin et al's [61] stress- and strain-based model of fracture.

Figure 24 presents the results of both LSY corrections. The figure depicts the T_0 mean values derived from the FRACTESUS 0.16T-C(T) results in comparison with their reference T_0 values from larger specimens. The T_0 mean values are given for the original-uncorrected T_0 , T_0 based on SCK CEN correction and T_0 based on N&D correction.

The results do not provide a definitive conclusion. In terms of the weld materials investigated in the FRACTESUS project, the comparability improves using LSY corrections. The root mean square deviation for T_0 based mean values decreases from 40.49 °C down to 32.45 °C (SCK CEN correction) and 10.54 °C (N&D correction).

In terms of the base materials the picture is different. Here the comparability decreases using LSY corrections. From 10.96 °C to 13.57 °C (SCK CEN correction) and 37.19 °C (N&D correction). However, this is mainly driven by the 15kh2MFA-A results as one can see from the pictures.

Figure 24 – Comparison of large scale yielding corrected 0.16T C(T) T_0 results from the FRACTESUS partners with corresponding (average) T_0 reference results.

4.5.3 Test temperature selection

ASTM E1921 recommends that the test temperature should be close to the expected reference temperature and mandates that the data is distributed in the temperature range $T_0 \pm 50^\circ\text{C}$. For small specimens, tests close to T_0 generally exceed the validity limit associated with the loss of small-scale yielding. On the other hand, testing at too low temperatures ($T - T_0 < 50^\circ\text{C}$) also leads to invalid data. In the lower shelf, multiple crack initiators are generally active and hence the weakest link theory with a single crack initiation site is no longer valid.

While censoring of data in large sample pools is generally not a big problem, censoring in smaller pools (for example for neutron irradiated specimens) can be a cause of concern as the validity criterion of ASTM E1921, i.e., $\sum r_i \cdot n_i \geq 1$ might not be fulfilled. For the selection of test temperatures, two competing aspects must be considered:

- testing at comparatively high temperatures close to T_0 to improve the quality of the Master Curve fit,
- testing at lower temperature to avoid censoring, but not below $T_0 - 50^\circ\text{C}$.

To minimize the number of tests that need censoring, HZDR has developed a strategy to select test temperatures based on censoring statistics [62].

The censoring statistics of mini-CT specimens can be described by the *tanh* function as follows:

$$P_c = 0.5 + 0.5 \cdot \tanh[c \cdot (T - T_0 + T_{sh})].$$

The large data set used in [51] (also including FRACTESUS data) provided the following fit parameters: $c = 0.056$ and $T_{sh} = 7.9$ K, see **Figure 25**. The data points in **Figure 25** represent relative frequencies of censored data in temperature intervals of 5 °C for $T - T_0$.

Figure 25 – Tanh-fit of the censoring probability plotted against $T - T_0$.

This description provides the possibility to establish a strategy for the selection of test temperatures. The temperatures of the first 3-5 tests must be selected based on the expected reference temperature ($T_{0,exp}$), e.g. based on NDT or T_{41} . The temperature interval $T_{0,exp} - 30$ °C < T < $T_{0,exp} - 25$ °C is a reasonable choice. Based on these first few data points, a preliminary T_0 can be calculated. The selection of the temperature of the next test is based on a target censoring probability:

$$T = T_0 - T_{sh} + \frac{1}{c} \cdot \arctan \left[\frac{P_{c,trg} - 0.5}{0.5} \right],$$

which corresponds to the first equation rearranged for solving T . The target censoring probability $P_{c,trg}$ is chosen in dependence of two parameters, $s_{rn} = \sum r_i n_i$ and r/N , calculated from the currently available test data (where r is the number of uncensored valid data and N is the total number of valid data). The following approach is used:

$$P_{c,trg} = 0.05 + 0.9 \cdot \left[\min \left(\frac{s_{rn}}{3}, 1 \right) \right]^p \cdot \left[\frac{r}{N} \right]^q,$$

i.e., $0.05 \leq P_{c,trg} \leq 0.95$. The parameters are $p = 0.7$ and $q = 1.1$, which ensures that the following condition is fulfilled: $P_{c,trg} < 0.5 \quad \forall \quad s_{rn} < 1$ and $r/N < 0.5$.

Thus, each new test temperature is selected based on the results of the previous tests.

4.5.4 Specimen set size

The required number of tests in a Master Curve dataset must be greater when using sub-sized specimens compared to standard-sized specimens. This is evidenced by T_0 analyses utilizing randomly selected data sets of varying sizes and following the standard multi-temperature procedure as outlined in section 10.2 of ASTM E1921-21. Such analyses were conducted the both the unirradiated and irradiated materials. The data subsets were generated from the full range of valid test results provided by the laboratories participating in the round robin.

To achieve a target standard deviation of $\sigma_{T_0} < 7^\circ\text{C}$, considered a reasonable threshold, the minimum required number of data points for a T_0 analysis should be $N_t \geq 16$. While this number of specimens would allow the predicted T_0 to converge to a consistent value for the dataset, it may not necessarily lead to a value of T_0 which is directly comparable with measurements on larger samples if the steel investigated is inhomogeneous (or does not follow the Master curve). The evolution of σ_{T_0} with N_t for five different materials is shown in **Figure 26**.

Figure 26 – The average standard deviation around T_0 with the number of tests N_t .

The suggested best practice suggested in **Error! Reference source not found.** based on the analysis of MC(T) data is to test at least 30 specimens so that a reliable assessment of inhomogeneity can be performed according to ASTM E1921 Appendix X5. The analysis of T_m (the temperature at which the median toughness is 100 MPa $\sqrt{\text{m}}$ in an inhomogeneous dataset analyzed according to the multimodal Master curve method) and σ_{T_m} – margin-adjusted 5% lower bound are then likely to be representative of data from larger specimens.

If fewer specimens are available, such that the refined approaches from ASTM E1921 cannot be applied, it has been suggested to use the simpler methods (with at least 16 specimens), but increase the magnitude of σ associated with T_0 by an uncertainty associated to material inhomogeneity (in which the $\sigma_{\text{material variability}}$ is taken as at least 7°C for a base metal or 19°C for a weld).

$$\sigma_{total}^2 = \sigma_{T_0}^2 + \sigma_{material\ variability}^2$$

Extrapolation using the $2\sigma_{T_0}$ margin adjustment to T_{0scrn} would then provide a reasonable description of the 5% lower bound to the 1T-C(T) data.

4.5.5 Manufacturing recommendations

One of the key issues with miniaturizing toughness specimens is the resulting increasing difficulty of machining and aligning small specimens within acceptable tolerances. The acceptable tolerances on all dimensions in a C(T) specimen is mandated by ASTM E1820 as $\pm 0.013 W$. This equals to about $\pm 0.10 \text{ mm}$

for a MC(T) specimen. This is a very tight tolerance, especially when specimens need to be fabricated in a hot cell environment.

It is recommended that to notice issues during fabrication, as well as other stages of in-cell work, a well-designed camera system is used. Also, for a successful pre-cracking, it must be ensured that the holes for the load pins are precisely aligned, i.e. exactly perpendicular to the specimen's side faces. Specimen fabrication may be done by electrical discharge machining (EDM) or classical milling. The advantages and drawbacks of EDM and milling are compared in **Table 8**.

Table 8 – Comparison between indicating advantages and drawbacks of EDM and milling.

	EDM	Milling
Precision	High overall accuracy but less control with respect to sharp angles.	Less overall accuracy but high accuracy with respect to sharp angles. Accurate and consistent notch radii when using a dedicated milling head. The milling heads wear off and loose accuracy over time.
Human error	As little as two times clamping/centering of the test piece. Little human intervention needed and less probability for errors.	Up to five to six times clamping/centering of the test piece. A lot of human intervention needed and more probability for errors.
Efficiency	Easy to machine a series of samples in one go. Largely automated. Up to two times faster than milling.	Every sample is machined individually. Labor intensive. Up to two times slower than EDM.
Finish	Cu implantation and stronger oxidation of the surface	
Maintenance	Considerable amount of used wire as active waste; regular change of filters for waste water.	Milling heads lose precision due to wear.

To ensure “straightness” of the pre-crack front, ASTM E1921 also imposes a criterion, which requires that the average starting fatigue pre-crack size derived from the physical measurements post-testing (as described in ASTM E1921 section 8.8.1) does not differ from each physical measurement by more than $0.1(b_0B_N)^{1/2}$. However, the FRACTESUS data showed that inclusion of data from specimens with “invalid” pre-crack shape (based on the above requirement), does not excessively affect the reference temperature. If there is otherwise insufficient data to derive a valid T_0 (more likely when irradiated materials are investigated), the inclusion of those data could be useful.

FRACTESUS partners have reported that fatigue pre-cracking with crack opening displacement (COD) measured at the front face provides acceptable crack fronts, while the COD measurement at the load-line during pre-cracking turned out to be unreliable, especially at high fatigue frequencies that are potentially due to test frame vibrations and other factors. If the estimation of crack length by unloading compliance measurement turns out to be unreliable, it should be combined with optical measurements at the specimen.

To conclude, it is well known from FEM simulations that side grooves maintain the plane strain conditions towards the side faces of the FT specimens. In contrast, specimens without side grooves exhibit a lower stress triaxiality at the sides, which relates to a lower crack opening stress. Thus, side-grooves should promote crack propagation initiation along the entire length of the effective section area.

In the fractography work, it was found that most initiation sites are located in the central half of the specimen, well away from the regions of slant fracture and within the parts of the specimen calculated to be in small-scale yielding. It seems very likely that the strong concentration of the initiators in the specimen center is due to the missing side grooves in all tested MC(T) specimens. This is underpinned by literature data from side grooved and non-side grooved specimens in which initiation sites appear more tightly confined close to the specimen mid-plane in the absence of side-grooving. However, the effect of side grooving on the reference temperature was shown to be insignificant. Therefore, the omission of side grooves is possible and saves fabrication work, especially in a hot cell environment.

4.5.6 Interactions with other projects

Throughout the execution of the FRACTESUS project, frequent interactions with other ongoing international activities took place. During special seminars and project meetings, the projects KleinProben, MEACTOS, ENTENTE, INCEFA-SCALE, STRUMAT-LTO and DELISA LTO were presented to the FRACTESUS participants and vice versa. As a result, return of experience as well as mechanical data could be exchanged. Additional interactions with international academic and industrial professionals took place during dedicated FRACTESUS sessions at the ASME Pressure Vessel & Piping Conference.

Table 9 summarizes the main interactions of the FRACTESUS project with other international activities.

Table 9 – Summary of the main interactions of the FRACTESUS project with other international activities.

Date	Event	Description
8 Feb. 2022	FRACTESUS 4th Executive Committee Meeting Virtual, Teams	The STRUMAT-LTO project was presented to the FRACTESUS ExCom members. Return of experience on MC(T) testing in FRACTESUS and fracture toughness data from STRUMAT-LTO could be exchanged. Also a common session on the PVP2024 and participation in each other's workshops/seminars was agreed.
8 – 9 Nov. 2022	FRACTESUS half-yearly progress meeting Lakehouse Auditorium 2 Mol, Belgium	The KleinProben project was presented to the FRACTESUS participants. The data obtained from the KleinProben project is available to the FRACTESUS project.
15 Dec. 2022	Overview article in EPJ Nuclear Sci. Technol.	An overview of the FRACTESUS, INCEFA-SCALE and MEACTOS projects were jointly presented in the article EPJ Nuclear Sci. Technol. 8 (2022) 42 (2022), https://doi.org/10.1051/epjn/2022033
22 Feb. 2023	FRACTESUS 6th Executive Committee Meeting Virtual, Teams	The DELISA-LTO project as well as some technical highlights were presented to the FRACTESUS ExCom members. The scientific approaches and techniques are similar in both

		projects. Fracture toughness data on 0.5T-C(T) specimens from DELISA-LTO can be shared with FRACTESUS. Participation in each other's workshops/seminars was agreed.
1 Jun. 2023	ENTENTE Exploitation team meeting Virtual, Zoom	The FRACTESUS project was presented during the ENTENTE Exploitation team meeting. During the discussion it was agreed that the FRACTESUS data will be formatted allowing for an easy integration into the ENTENTE database.
6 Jun. 2023	DELISA-LTO 1st yearly meeting Virtual, Zoom	The FRACTESUS project was presented during the DELISA-LTO 1 st yearly meeting. The scientific approaches and techniques are similar in both projects. Fracture toughness data on 0.5T-C(T) specimens from DELISA-LTO can be shared with FRACTESUS. Participation in each other's workshops/seminars was agreed.
7 Jun. 2023	FRACTESUS half-yearly progress meeting Virtual, Teams	The DELISA-LTO project as well as some technical highlights were presented to the FRACTESUS participants. The scientific approaches and techniques are similar in both projects. Fracture toughness data on 0.5T-C(T) specimens from DELISA-LTO can be shared with FRACTESUS. Participation in each other's workshops/seminars was agreed.
16 Jul. – 21 Aug. 2023	ASME PVP 2023 Westin Peachtree Plaza Atlanta, GA, USA	Presentation of the FRACTESUS project and presentations related to FRACTESUS results were provided during two special sessions. A total 7 FRACTESUS related papers were published.
19 – 20 Sep. 2023	INCEFA-SCALE Mid-term Seminar Paraninfo de la Universidad de Cantabria, c/ Sevilla 6 Santader, Spain	The FRACTESUS project was presented during the INCEFA-SCALE Mid-term seminar. The seminar/workshop was aimed at PhD students; professional engineers and researchers working in the fields of fatigue, environmental fatigue or structural integrity; highly experienced researchers and engineers wishing to update their knowledge and share experiences.
12 – 13 Dec. 2023	FRACTESUS half-yearly progress meeting Lakehouse Auditorium 2 Mol, Belgium	The latest news of the ASTM committee E08.07 on ASTM standards E1921 and E1820 was presented to the FRACTESUS participants. A call for support was launched to the FRACTESUS participants was launched to potentially relax the crack size variation requirements in section 8.6.3 of ASTM E1921

<p>28-30 May 2024</p>	<p>STRUMAT-LTO Summer School ÚJV Řež, 130 Hlavní 250 68 Husinec Czech Republic</p>	<p>The FRACTESUS project and its main advances were presented during the STRUMAT-LTO Summer School. The event aimed to ensure the transfer of knowledge between retiring and new members of the nuclear workforce. In a conference format, several nuclear experts presented the latest results and findings of STRUMAT-LTO and other sister projects such as ENTENTE, FRACTESUS and DELISA, followed by a series of expert lectures.</p>
<p>28 Jul. – 2 Aug. 2024</p>	<p>ASME PVP 2024 Hyatt Regency Bellevue Bellevue, WA, USA</p>	<p>Presentation of the FRACTESUS project and presentations related to FRACTESUS results were provided during one special session. An additional contribution from FRACTESUS consortium was presented in an additional session dedicated to small-scale testing. A total 5 FRACTESUS related papers were published.</p>
<p>10 – 11 Sep. 2024</p>	<p>FRACTESUS final seminar Paraninfo de la Universidad de Cantabria, c/ Sevilla 6 Santader, Spain</p>	<p>The main results of the projects KleinProben, INCEFA-SCALE, STRUMAT-LTO and ENTENTE will be presented during the FRACTESUS final seminar.</p>

4.6 WP6 – Dissemination, training and education and data management

The present work package is focused on the project’s communication towards, the wide public, nuclear stakeholders and specialists in the field. The work package implements a data management plan such that correct and uniform reporting of experimental results is assured. As such, the data is procured following the FAIR principles and free to use by future initiatives thereby avoiding misinterpretations and inadmissible variability of the results caused by different laboratories or experimental procedures.

The work is organized following the three tasks below:

- T6.1: Communication and dissemination
- T6.2: Training and education
- T6.3: Data management

All details of the activities are found in nine different deliverables. The data management plan and its subsequent versions are found in deliverable **D6.8**, while the project’s testing protocols and reporting formats are presented in deliverable **D6.9**. The details of the two special FRACTESUS sessions at the PVP conference in 2023 and 2024 (see **Table 9**) are reported in deliverables **D6.4** and **D6.6**; the FRACTESUS seminar organized at the University of Cantabria (**Table 9**) with 73 participants from 15 countries and the report on training and education activities are described in deliverables **D6.5** and **D6.7**. All communication activities on social/scientific/professional networks and to the scientific community are reported in deliverables **D6.1**, **D6.2** and **D6.3**.

Participants representing the project have participated in 26 different international conferences and events, thereby providing 38 presentations. The project consortium has generated in 13 papers on scientific journals indexed in the Journal Citation Report (JCR), 22 papers included in conference proceedings indexed in Scopus, and 6 additional non-indexed publications.

As a result of the experimental test program, more than 600 datasets were uploaded to Zenodo and Open Aire, each one with its corresponding DOI.

4.7 WP7 – General management

4.7.1 Objectives

This work package provides a clear framework and all necessary support mechanisms to enable a smooth project workflow. SCK CEN is responsible for the coordination of all R&D activities, and carrying out diverse administrative (progress reports, deliverables) and financial (fund distribution, monitoring of expenses) tasks; smooth exchange of information between the involved parties; timely submission of high-quality deliverables to the EC; and effective handling of problems (administrative, financial, ethical).

The work package is organized in three main tasks:

- T7.1: Website (public + member)
- T7.2: Administration (deliverables, milestones, financial reporting)
- T7.3: Meetings (executive meetings, progress meetings, general assembly)

With the present deliverable, all 31 deliverables (and milestones) of the FRACTESUS project have been achieved. The project management platform where all relevant data can be found is described in deliverable **D7.1**. The project's review reports halfway and at the end of the project are described in deliverables **D7.2** and **D7.3**, respectively.

4.8 WP8 – Ethics requirements

This work package sets out the 'ethics requirements' that the project must comply with. The two requirements are summarized in the two deliverables **D8.1** and **D8.2**.

Deliverable **D8.1** requires that the host institution must confirm that it has appointed a Data Protection Officer (DPO) and the contact details of the DPO are made available to all data subjects involved in the research. For host institutions not required to appoint a DPO under the GDPR a detailed data protection policy for the project must be kept on file (to be specified in the grant agreement).

Deliverable **D8.2** requires that in case activities undertaken in non-EU countries raise ethics issues, the applicants must ensure that the research conducted outside the EU is legal in at least one EU Member State. This must be specified in the grant agreement. Copies of import/export authorizations, as required by national/EU legislation must be kept on file (to be specified in the grant agreement).

5 Conclusion

To investigate the equivalence between fracture toughness data obtained from MC(T) and larger specimens, more 600 fracture toughness tests were performed on six (four base and two welds) different RPV relevant steels in irradiated and unirradiated state. To this experimental round robin, 14 different laboratories participated. In addition, numerical models were implemented in finite element models to support the experimental tests.

For all base materials agreement between data obtained from MC(T) and large specimens is satisfactory when accounting for macroscopic inhomogeneities in the steel (A508 Cl.3 and A533B JRQ). For weld materials, the analysis is more subtle: while agreement between MC(T) and large specimen data is satisfactory for ANP-5 when accounting for material heterogeneity, this is not the case for the 73W weldment, both in irradiated and unirradiated state.

For weldments, the scale of inhomogeneity in a weld was such that a 1T-C(T) specimen would sample across several weld beads, whereas a MC(T) specimen would sample less than a single weld bead. This suggests that metals and especially weld metals can exhibit microstructural inhomogeneity on a scale that significantly affects toughness testing. Both weld and base metals are likely to contain multiple constituent regions of substantial size such as recrystallized and as-deposited regions of a weld bead or islands of ferrite, bainite or martensite that reflect the dendrite spacing typical of castings. Each region contains a distribution of weak links which may or may not overlap with those in other regions. This underscores the necessity of testing a larger number of specimens to ensure an accurate assessment of inhomogeneity.

Finally, we note that all MC(T) complete data sets are inhomogeneous, regardless of the homogeneity or inhomogeneity in the reference data set. The small sampling volume combined with the weakest link theory interpretation means that local differences in the material may result in a large variation from one tested MC(T) specimen to another. Thus, rather than MC(T) specimens misinterpreting homogeneous materials as being inhomogeneous, MC(T) specimens are more adept at identifying inhomogeneity than larger specimens.

This last point should be taken as a strength of the use of MC(T), i.e., the capability to sample material properties very locally if desired. When a complete block or plate needs to be characterized, MC(T) specimens need to be collected from various locations within the block or plate in the same manner as with larger specimens.

Overall, fractography supports the use of toughness data from mini-CT specimens, if the tests are valid according to ASTM E1921-21. Ductility at edges of specimens does not dominate nucleation and the asymmetry of crack front does not dominate nucleation either. The fracture mode is likely to be unaffected by specimen size. A concentration of initiation sites in the central half of the specimen is observed due to the missing side grooves. However, since the relation between K_{Jc} and the distance to the initiation site is unaffected by specimen size, the stress and strain conditions at fracture initiation will be the same in the miniature and larger specimens.

As most important guidelines for MC(T) testing we mention:

- A test temperature selection algorithm was developed based on censoring statistics to minimize the number of invalid tests.
- A data set of 30 specimens or more is recommended to perform a reliable assessment of inhomogeneity according to ASTM E1921-21 Appendix X5.
- A set size of at least 16 specimens recommended to achieve $\sigma_{T_0} \leq 7$ °C.
- In absence of a bimodal or multimodal analysis, an additional uncertainty related to material variability of 7 °C is proposed for a base metal.

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